

CLIMATE FINANCING MECHANISM IN BANGLADESH: DOES THE CLIMATE CHANGE TRUST FUND PLAY ITS ROLE PROPERLY?

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Abstract:

This Study seeks to analyze the trends of fund flow of Climate Change Trust Fund, a national window of climate financing in Bangladesh. The main objectives of this study are to analyze the process of enactment of Climate Change Trust Fund with special attention to its fiduciary management continuing for long nine years and also to identify the utilization gaps of this fund in terms to policy and practices. This is an explanatory and qualitative research. The result of this study shows that the Climate Change Trust Fund (CCTF) has mainly utilized its fund for Water Resources, Infrastructure, Agriculture, Forestry and Biodiversity conservation. Projects have been implemented both on Adaptation, Mitigation and cross-cutting (Combining adaptation and mitigation) aspects with greater preference and priority on Adaptation issue. It is noted that eighteen Ministries along with their affiliated agencies have implemented the Climate Change Trust Funded Projects throughout the country. Among the six thematic areas of Bangladesh Climate Change Strategy and Action Plan (BCCSAP, 2009), thematic area, T3: infrastructure and T1: Food Security, Social Protection and Health have got the highest priority to the decision makers for Funding. In terms of project number, maximum infrastructural activities under CCTF were implemented by Local Government Division where as large amount of money were allocated to the Ministry of Water Resources for infrastructure, rehabilitation and repair activities at the coastal zones in the country. Since Bangladesh is catastrophe prone, reasonably and inevitably, the infrastructure development is more essential at the coastal areas than other activities on climate financing. It is also envisaged that most of the activities of CCTF where funds were allocated were some routine works of concerned ministries while a few number of activities were innovative and predominantly addressed to the climate induced loss and damages in the country. It is because perhaps, the criteria for financing on the climate induced activities were not mentioned clearly in the strategy

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paper and there had been no mandate or provision for the feasibility study of the project before the approval process. These are some of the limitations of the CCTF and BCCT that manages this fund, nevertheless, the establishment of such kind of generous fund and the climate induced activities so far implemented play an important role to develop the adaptive capacity of local community of Bangladesh to addresses the challenges of climate change impacts and aftermath.

Keywords: Bangladesh Climate Change Trust Fund, Bangladesh Climate Change Trust, Climate Finance, Bangladesh Climate Change Strategy and Action Plan, 2009, adaptation, mitigation, thematic area, vulnerability

1. Introduction

Bangladesh is one of the largest deltas in the world which is highly vulnerable to natural disasters because of its geographical location, flat and low-lying landscape, population density, poverty, illiteracy, lack of institutional setup etc. Moreover, Bangladesh is one of the most climate vulnerable countries in the world due to global warming and sea level rise. Giving the utmost priority on climate change issues, the government of Bangladesh has developed Bangladesh Climate Change Strategy and Action Plan, (BCCSAP) in 2009. It is one of the first landmark documents among the developing countries with the vision to eradicate poverty and achieve economic and social wellbeing through a pro-poor climate change resilience strategy. Climate Change Trust Act was enacted in 2010. To implement the action plan, a dedicated Climate Change Trust Fund was established under the revenue budget of Government. At the same time, another fund was developed with the contribution of development partners, called Bangladesh Climate Change Resilience fund (BCCRF). It was managed by the World Bank. On the other hand, Climate Change Trust Fund was managed by Bangladesh Climate Change Trust (BCCT) under the Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change. So far, in CCTF from 2009-2010 to 2017-2018, Tk. 3,200 crore BDT has been allocated. CCTF is the major significant climate financing mechanism of the government in Bangladesh, covering a large area under the national support rather than the global one. It is the main source of national funding mechanism regarding climate change issues in Bangladesh. The funds initiated its operational activities from 2009 which is still going on. Till date, 512 projects have been implemented by different government agencies under Climate Change Trust Fund. The specific objectives of the study are to examine the fiduciary management of Bangladesh Climate Change Trust Fund, to evaluate the performance of Fund disbursement process and finally to identify the funding gaps of Climate Change Trust Fund in terms of Policy and practices. This is perhaps the first study of this kind that takes into account the evaluation of the Financing Mechanism of Climate Change Trust Fund. The study culminates with conclusions summarizing the most important research findings, suggestions and recommendations as well.

2. Literature Review

Climate finance has emerged as a pivotal point in global negotiations. The study examines some significant global climate policy papers and institutions such as UNFCCC, IPCC, COP, Paris agreement as well as global financing initiatives like Global Environmental Facility (GEF), Adaptation Fund, Green Climate Fund (GCF), Least Development Countries Fund (LDCF), Special Climate Change Fund (SCCF), Climate Investment Funds etc. While the new landscape of climate change funds provide increased resources, they also invite newer and increased complexity. Requirements, processes and reporting can differ depending on the nature of the funds. Various countries are often faced with the challenge of identifying which funds are appropriate for them, how to collect resources, how to blend them together, how to coordinate the actions funded by them and how to develop the methods to monitor and evaluate the results. A National Climate Fund (NCF) is a tool that supports countries to direct finance towards climate change projects and programs by facilitating the collection, combining/blending, coordination of, and accounting for climate finance. NCFs are country-owned funds that can access and manage finance from a variety of domestic and international sources and deliver them to support climate actions of national priority (Adapt Asia-Pacific, 2012).

Climate Change Trust Fund is one of the important NCFs in Bangladesh. Climate Change Trust Fund was established to implement Bangladesh Climate Change Strategy and Action plan, 2009 to address the adverse impact of climate change. There are six thematic areas in BCCSAP, 2009. The plan is clearly a knowledge strategy, which needs to be transformed into an implementation strategy by the respective ministries and departments. While it identified six thematic areas, it did not prioritize action on the ground within the context of vulnerability, which is critical for allocating resources to deal with immediate and urgent needs. The study finds that 67% of Projects under CCTF covers the thematic area; T3: Infrastructure, while the amount of projects on thematic area T4: Research and knowledge management and T6: capacity building and institutional strengthening are quite pitiable. In BCCSAP, 2009 the climate induced vulnerable sector is not identified, that's why money did not flow in a right way at the climate induced area. Moreover, top-down approach in project selection didn't blend the demand with the allocation. Besides, the fund flow reduced day by day while the demand of adopting projects increased. The study identifies all these challenges and concludes through a way forward to overcome the deficiencies.

3. Methodology

This was a qualitative and explanatory study. All data and information of the study are collected from secondary sources, field level observation and key informants. The relevant documents of 512 projects which were implemented under Climate Change Trust Fund were individually examined and few of these projects were visited at the

field level during the research time. The findings of the study were scrutinized through textual analysis and percentage frequencies which are presented as tables in the report. These are then corroborated in the discussion of the results with content analysis as well as with the outcomes from field observation. No theoretical framework has been used to conduct the study.

3.1 Bangladesh Climate Change Trust Fund at a Glance

The Government of Bangladesh developed Bangladesh Climate Change Strategy and Action Plan (BCCSAP) in 2008 which was updated in 2009. BCCSAP focused on medium and long-term actions based on six thematic pillars; food security, social protection and health, comprehensive disaster management, infrastructure, research and knowledge management, mitigation and low carbon development, and capacity building and institutional strengthening. Recognizing the uncertainties and inadequacies of international adaptation finance from both multilateral and bilateral sources, the Government of Bangladesh decided to establish the Bangladesh Climate Change Trust Fund (BCCTF) based on revenue from the national budget, within a legal mandate by the Climate Change Trust Act passed in Parliament in 2010 (www.bcct.gov.bd).

An independent Board of Trustees, chaired by the Minister for Environment and Forest and Climate Change, oversees the governance and management of the Climate Change Trust Fund. There are 17 members, of which two are from CSOs and the rest are from government ministries and departments. The two non-government members serve for a period of three years, while the other members serve for the period that they hold that particular position (The first Board has been in place and operational since 2010). Members serve without any financial compensation and are expected to play a neutral role, without bias to the ministry, department or organization to which they belong. Ensuring total neutrality is a challenge however, decision-making through consensus, and openness and transparency in the decision-making process serve to promote neutrality. In addition, the Parliamentary Standing Committee responsible for oversight of the Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change also serves as another check point 'for the decisions of the Board. There is also a 12-member Technical Committee which is responsible for reviewing proposals, and advising the Board of Trustees. It is headed by the Secretary to the Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change, and includes members from key government ministries and departments, and two representatives from Civil Society Organizations (www.bcct.gov.bd).

Bangladesh Climate Change Trust (BCCT) is a statutory body under Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change, formed under the provision of Climate Change Trust Act, 2010 to manage Climate Change Trust Fund. It provides administrative and organizational support to the Trustee Board and the Technical Committee. Besides, BCCT monitors the projects at the field level.

Both BCCT and individual projects are audited by Comptroller and Auditor General (CAG) of Bangladesh. The Trustee Board is also required to submit to the Government an Annual Report on its activities of the previous fiscal year. BCCT is answerable to questions raised by Honorable Members of Parliament (MPs) in *Jatiya Sangshad*. Its activities are also discussed in the meetings of Parliamentary Standing Committee on Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change. (<http://www.bcct.gov.bd>). The BCCTF, meanwhile, is an exemplary initiative that authorized the use of national revenue to finance climate action, despite other urgent national priorities like poverty reduction. However, this makes it all the more important that public funds are used effectively, and prioritizes the need of the most vulnerable areas and communities. It is also imperative that the decisions of the Board of Trustees are not influenced by partisan politics and political interest; given that, most of the members are Ministers. Instead, the members should use the opportunity to reinforce political commitment to fight climate change.

4. Result and Discussion

In Table 1, the allocation of Climate Change Trust Fund during last nine years has been presented. It is to be mentioned here that CCTF started its journey in the year 2010 and is still operational to its fullest capacity. From the base year up to the fiscal year 2017-18, Tk. 3,200 crore BDTⁱⁱ has been allocated from the revenue budget of Government for the Climate Change Trust Fund (CCTF).

Table 1: Annual Allocation of Climate Change Trust Fund

S.I No	Financial Year	Allocated Money (BDT in crore)
1.	2009-2010	700
2.	2010-2011	700
3.	2011-2012	700
4.	2012-2013	400
5.	2013-2014	200
6.	2014-2015	200
7.	2015-2016	100
8.	20016-2017	100
9.	2017-2018	100
Total		3,200

The number of approved projects and fund disbursement varied due to annual allocation of the Fund as well as the decision of Trustee Board. The year to year analyses during last nine years are mentioned below:

- a. In the fiscal year 2009-10, Bangladesh government allocated 700 crore in BDT Climate Change Trust Fund. 32 projects with an estimated cost of 343.07 BDT were adopted at 6 Districts in 8 Divisions of the country. Maximum numbers of

ⁱⁱ 1 USD = 80 BDT

- projects amounting to 102.85 crore in BDT were approved for the various affiliated agencies under Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change this year. On the other hand, surplus of fund were distributed at Dhaka Division. Out of the six thematic areas, the themes on Food Security, social Protection and Health, Infrastructure and Mitigation and Low Carbon Development got the highest priority in terms of fund flow.
- b. In the fiscal year 2010-11, 700 crore in BDT were allocated and 24 projects were taken with an estimated cost of 310.74 crore in BDT at 10 different Districts of 8 Divisions in the country. 152.09 crore in BDT were allocated under the Ministry of Water Resources, which was the largest in amount this year. Maximum projects were taken in Khulna Division, which was considered to be the most climate vulnerable zone in the country. At the same time, maximum projects were implemented under the thematic area Infrastructure of BCCSAP, 2009.
 - c. In the fiscal year 2011-12, 700 crore in BDT were allocated from CCTF and 37 projects were adopted with an estimated cost of 491 Crore in BDT at 22 Districts of 8 Divisions. Most of the funds were allocated under the Ministry of Water Resources with an allocation of 295.37 crore in BDT. A total of 25 projects were implemented under the theme Infrastructure and 11 projects were implemented at Dhaka Division.
 - d. In the fiscal year 2012-13, 400 crore in BDT were allocated. A total of 49 projects were taken with an estimated cost of 447.54 crore in BDT at 30 Districts of 8 Divisions in the country. Out of 49, a total of 27 projects with an estimated cost of Tk. 264.41 crore in BDT were allocated for the Ministry of Water Resources. 11 projects were taken in Dhaka Division with an estimated cost of 53.26 crore in BDT and again, the theme Infrastructure had the largest number of the projects under this jurisdiction.
 - e. In the fiscal year 2013-14, 200 crore in BDT were allocated and 76 projects were adopted with an estimated cost of 338.78 crore in BDT at 33 Districts in 8 Divisions. This time, a total of 45 projects with an estimated cost of 248.81 crore in BDT were allocated for the Ministry of Water Resources. 20 projects were taken for Chittagong Division with an estimated cost of 112.21 crore in BDT and under the theme, T: 3, infrastructure registering 62 projects. It is to be mentioned here that projects were funded both from the annual allocation and interest of the fixed deposits.
 - f. In the fiscal year 2014-15, Tk. 200 crore in BDT were allocated and 87 projects were taken with an estimated cost of 380.62 crore in BDT at 30 Districts in 8 Divisions in the country. 56 projects with an estimated cost of 222.83 crore in BDT were allocated for the Local Government Division, Ministry of Local Government and Rural Development and cooperatives. 30 projects were taken in Barisal Division with an estimated cost of 168.44 crore in BDT and a total of 40 projects fell under the theme Food Security, Social Protection and Health. This

time also, the projects were funded both from the annual allocation and interest of the fixed deposits.

- g. In the fiscal year 2015-16, 100 crore in BDT were allocated and 73 projects were taken with an estimated cost of 199.09 crore in BDT at 30 Districts of 8 Divisions. 46 projects with an estimated cost of 125.25 crore in BDT were allocated to the Local Government Division, Ministry of Local Government, Rural Development and cooperatives. 21 projects were taken in Barisal Division with an estimated cost of 494.89 crore in BDT. This time, the theme, T: 3, Infrastructure registered 49 projects. Projects were financed both from the annual allocation and interest of the fixed deposits.
- h. In the fiscal year 2016-17, 100 crore in BDT were allocated and 74 projects were taken with an estimated cost of 209.14 crore in BDT at 38 Districts in 8 Divisions. 57 projects with an estimated cost of 161.36 crore in BDT were allocated to the Local Government Division, Ministry of Local Government, Rural Development and cooperatives. 19 projects were taken in Barisal Division with an estimated cost of 76.71 crore in BDT. This time, the theme, T: 3, Infrastructure got 49 projects. As in the previous year, projects were taken both from the annual allocation and interest of the fixed deposits.
- i. In the fiscal year 2017-18, 100 crore in BDT were allocated and 60 projects were taken with an estimated cost of 184.57 crore in BDT at 35 Districts in 8 Divisions. 41 projects with an estimated cost of 102.04 crore in BDT were allocated to the Local Government Division, Ministry of Local Government, Rural Development and cooperatives. 32 projects were taken in Barisal Division with an estimated cost of 116.09 crore in BDT. This time, the theme, T: 3, Infrastructure registered 38 projects. It is also to be mentioned that projects were taken both from the annual allocation and interest of the fixed deposits.

Eighteen Ministries including Ministry of Environment, Forests and Climate Change were the Stakeholders of Climate Change Trust Funded Projects. Under these Ministries, various line agencies and affiliated departments are/were implementing the projects at the field level. Among all these ministries, Ministry of Local Government, Rural Development and Cooperatives and Ministry of Water Resources are the largest stakeholders in terms of the implementation of the CCTF Projects. So far, maximum numbers of projects were implemented by Ministry of Local Government, Rural Development and Cooperatives but the Ministry of Water Resources received larger amount of funds in comparison to LGED Ministry and other ministries as well. The following table 2 represents the number of projects with estimated cost for each implementing ministries:

Table 2: Ministry wise Fund Disbursement along with the project number

S.I No	Name of Ministry	Projects Number	Cost (BDT in crore)
1	Ministry of Water Resources	142	1119.57
2	Local Government Division	243	867.06

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3	Ministry of Environment and Forest and Climate Change	57	368.32
4	Ministry of Agriculture	17	133.55
5	Ministry of Disaster Management and Relief	7	123.52
6	Rural Development Division	6	72.49
7	Ministry of Power, Energy and Mineral Resources	3	56.02
8	Ministry of Shipping	3	51.76
9	Ministry of Education	15	48.21
10	Ministry of Defense	8	44.21
11	Ministry of Health and Family Welfare	2	20.12
12	Ministry of Science and Technology	2	19.31
13	Ministry of Women and Children Affairs	2	8.00
14	Ministry of Chittagong Hill tracks Affairs	1	6.53
15	Ministry of Fisheries and Livestock	1	2.00
16	Ministry of Home Affairs	1	2.00
17	Ministry of Civil Aviation	1	1.00
18	Ministry of Public Administration	1	0.19
	Total	512	2943.85

In Bangladesh Climate Change Strategy and Action Plan, (BCCSAP, 2009), there are six thematic areas with 44 programs. Projects under CCTF were implemented addressing the particular thematic area with specific programs.

Table 3: BCCSAP Themes

Theme 1: Food Security, Social Protection and Health	Relates to ensuring food and livelihood security, especially for the poorest and most vulnerable in society, including women and children. It focuses on the needs for food security, safe housing, employment and access to basic services, including health.
Theme 2: Comprehensive Disaster Management	This is to further strengthen the country's already proven disaster management systems to deal with increasingly frequent and severe natural calamities.
Theme 3: Infrastructure	This theme is to ensure that existing assets (e.g. coastal and river embankments) are well-maintained and fit-for-purpose and that urgently needed infrastructure (e.g. cyclone shelters and urban drainage) is put in place to deal with the likely impacts of climate change.
Theme 4: Research and Knowledge Management	This is to predict the likely scale and timing of climate change impacts on different sectors of the economy and socio-economic groups: to underpin future investment strategies; and to ensure that Bangladesh is networked into the latest global thinking on science, and best practices of climate change management.
Theme 5: Mitigation and Low Carbon Development	This theme is to evolve low carbon development options and implement these as the country's economy grows over the coming decades and the demand for energy increases.
Theme 6: Capacity Building and Institutional Strengthening	This theme is to enhance the capacity of government ministries and agencies, civil society and the private sector to meet the challenge of climate change and mainstream

So far, major projects implemented under CCTF, covered the thematic area of Infrastructure (T: 3) and next one is Food Security, social Protection and Health (T: 1). As a developing country, adaptation is given priority on climate change issues while some notable projects were also taken on Mitigation and Low Carbon Development to reduce the Carbon Emissions. Under the thematic area, T: 3, Infrastructure, most projects were implemented by Ministry of Water Resources and Local Government Division as a part of Adaptation. Schools cum cyclone shelter, cyclone resistant houses, river bank protection works are some of the major activities under this thematic area. Figure 1 illustrates thematic area-wise fund disbursement under CCTF.

Figure 1: Thematic area wise allocation under CCTF

Projects under CCTF were implemented in each of the 64 Districts under 8 Divisions in Bangladesh. Climate Change has diversified and multi-facet impacts on different areas and different sectors in the country. Due to its geographical position, Bangladesh has already been affected by different climate change factors and impacts. Severe cyclone, flash flood, increasing intensity of saline water, drought are the common phenomena regarding climate change issues. The vulnerable zones of the country were calculated due to the frequency of disasters and its impact. Considering these issues, projects under CCTF were taken all over the country but the priority and attention was given in the coastal belt region. Through the financial analysis of the data as exhibited above, it was found that that maximum number of projects and the allocated money were disbursed into the coastal regions like; Chittagong, Barisal and Khulna Divisions which are located at the southern part of the country and really facing the brunt and challenges of climate change atrocity. From the study, it is found that highest numbers of projects along with the biggest budget were allocated in Barisal and Chittagong divisions. Moreover, some projects were implemented in more than one

Division in the country. Figure 2 represents the project allocation according to the 8 Divisions in the country.

Figure 2: Division wise Fund flow under CCTF

Through the Climate Change Trust Fund (CCTF), during the last nine years period, lots of activities are taken into consideration to address the climate change issues at different levels. These activities are taken following the thematic area and programs addressed in the BCCSAP, 2009. But in true sense and from the prima facie observation, it becomes apparent that most and maximum of the activities performed under the banner of climate risk reduction is nothing but mere routine works or development activities of the concerned departments, agencies or affiliated bodies. It also sometimes appears that some of the activities or actions have been performed in the brand or name of climate change impacts artificially wearing the gown of climate nomenclature. The main stakeholders of CCTF Projects are Bangladesh Water Development Board (BWDB) but due to fund constraints, for the last few years, maximum projects under CCTF were implemented by different municipalities under Local Government Division (LGD). Construction of drainage improvement system and solar street lights are the main activities under the Local Government Engineering Division lately. Table 4 depicts the adaptation activities under CCTF:

Table 4: Accompanied Adaptation Activities under CCTF

Sl. No	Name of Activity	Quantity	Cost (crore in BDT)
1	River Bank Protection Work	172.21 km	494.81
2	Embankment cum Road	4216.794 km	252.72
3	Cyclone Resistant Houses	11415	166.7
4	Excavation/Re-excavation of khal/River	853.9 km	159.45
5	Construction of Regulator/ Sluice Gate	82	76.82
6	Number of Deep tube well Installed	7515	85.0445

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7	Production of Climate Tolerant Seeds	2825 M.ton	49.14
8	Rubber Dam for Irrigation	12400 sqm	18.56
9	School cum Cyclone Shelter	14	44.338
11	Construction of Culvert	4216.79 km	17.51
12	Construction of Bridges	55 km	7.57
13	Development of Roads	91.509	74.25

Besides adaptation activities from CCTF, a good number of mitigation activities were also implemented during last 7 years. Bangladesh is committed to reduce 5% emission in energy, transport and industry sector by 2030 with its own resources (Bangladesh NDC report, 2015). Table 5 exhibits the mitigation activities under CCTF.

Table 5: Accompanied Mitigation Activities under CCTF

S.I No	Name of Activity	Quantity	Cost (BDT in crore)
1	Construction of Drainage System	241.1442	289.42
2	Installation of Solar Home System	6,425	84.6
3	Installation of Biogas plant/Bio Fertilizer Plant	7,914	18.56
4	Installation of Improved Cook Stoves	92,8000	18.56
5	Plantation	32,33210	11.11
6	Raising of Seedlings	1,38714	32.48
7	Afforestation	120 km	12.11
8	Construction of Compost plant/waste management plant	17	18.67
9	Number of Solar Street Light Installed	1188	19.06
10	Environment Friendly Bus Terminal	1	10
11	Education Friendly Solar Light	20660	4
12	Solar Power Plant	2 (33KW)	2
13	Eco Park Development	7	37

5. Recommendations

Climate Change Trust Fund was established to address the challenges and adverse impacts of climate in Bangladesh. The fund was mainly utilized to implement the BCCSAP, 2009. BCCSAP is merely a guideline for initiating action on climate change issues. It provides some strategy and guideline but does not necessarily identify or pinpoints vulnerable sectors of climate induced atrocities. Hence, the money spent on this strategy paper is not worthy of bringing the fullest outcome. At such a juncture, it needs to be updated and accommodated to fit in the demand of the real investment, investment on the identified vulnerable sector. Thus, in BCCSAP, 2009 the climate induced vulnerable sector is not identified, that's why money did not flow in a right way at the climate induced area. To overcome the situation, the following suggestions are made from the study:

1. At the beginning of each fiscal year, priority should be fixed up by Ministry of Finance for taking projects within inter ministry and agency based on annual allocation.

2. Develop a benchmark to identify the climate induced risk/impacted activity or vulnerable area with the regular work/activities.
3. Risk mapping is necessary to identify the level of risk due to climate change and projects should be taken particularly fit in that climate induced areas.
4. Projects under CCTF should be taken to ensure the sustainability of proposed activities.
5. Priority should be given for taking projects proportionately from each of the thematic area in the upcoming revised BCCSAP.

6. Conclusion

It is globally recognized that the negative effect of climate change is a big threat for almost every country of the world. Realizing the importance of this issue, the People's Republic of Bangladesh adopted Bangladesh Climate Change Strategic Action Plan (BCCSAP in 2009 and created a fund from its revenue budget called Climate Change Trust Fund (CCTF). Being a vulnerable developing country, Bangladesh did not wait for assistance and donation from the developed countries, primarily responsible for such adverse effect of climate change. Rather Bangladesh formed a robust fund from its scarce resources to combat such vulnerability through self-financing. CCTF started its journey in the year 2010 and now it operates to its fullest capacity. From the base year up to the present time, so far BDT 3,500 in crore has been allocated from the revenue budget for the Climate Change Trust Fund (CCTF). 512 projects so far approved, 221 projects have already been successfully accomplished. CCTF has given topmost priority in funding those projects that pertain to Adaptation. Though Bangladesh has negligible role in terms of Carbon Emission, however, Mitigation has also been taken into active consideration and a good number of mitigation projects have been approved, implemented or are under execution. This is an academic research and this research is not in an extensive form due to the above mentioned limitations. This topic can be developed further by the other academic researchers by incorporating more activities and valuable inputs within the national financing framework in future research.

About the Author

Shakila Yasmin is a dedicated government service holder in Bangladesh. She has been working in Bangladesh Climate Change Trust (BCCT) under the Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change since 2010 in the capacity of Assistant Director (Development). Bangladesh Climate Change Trust is the only Public organization in Bangladesh which deals with the climate change issues. Shakila by education is an engineer. After joining in service, she completed her Masters in Disaster Management and Vulnerability studies from the University of Dhaka in Bangladesh.

References

1. Adapt Asia Pacific (2012). *Regional Clinic on the Design and Management of National Climate Funds*. Available at <http://www.adapt-asia.org/events/regional-clinic-design-and-management-national-climate-funds>.
2. Adger et al (1999), *Social vulnerability to climate change and the architecture of entitlements*. *Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies for Global Change*, PP (253-266)
3. Atteridge, Aaron (2009), SEI Policy Brief. Stockholm Environment Institute.) *Private sector finance and climate change adaptation: how can voluntary private finance support adaptations in developing countries*.
4. Flynn, Cassie. 2011. *Blending Climate Finance through National Climate Funds: A Guidebook for the design and establishment of national funds to achieve climate change priorities*. United Nations Development Programme. New York, USA.
5. International Institute for Environment and Development and Grantham Institute for Climate Change, London. Accessed 4 September 2011. <http://pubs.iied.org/pdfs/11501IIED>.
6. IPCC, (2001b). *Climate change 2001: The scientific basis. Contribution of working group I to the Third Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on climate change*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
7. IPCC, (2007). *IPCC Synthesis report*. Geneva, World Meteorological Organization (WMO), United Nations Environmental Program (UNEP).
8. IPCC, 2013. *The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* [Stocker et al (Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, pp1535
9. MOEF, (2009). *National Adaptation Programme of Action (NAPA)*. Ministry of Environment and Forests, Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, Dhaka, Bangladesh. pp.39.
10. Myers, N. 2002. *Environmental refugees: a growing phenomenon of the 21st century*. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society: Biological Sciences* 357: 609-613. National Research Council. 2007. *Tools and methods for estimating population at risk from natural disasters and complex humanitarian crises*. Washington, D.C.
11. Montes, Manuel. 2012. *Understanding the long-term finance needs of developing countries*.
12. Stadel Mann, et al (2011), *Accounting of private climate finance. Types of finance, data gaps and the 100-billion-dollar question*. *Climate Strategies Working Paper*. <http://www.climatestrategies.org/component/reports/category/71/331.html>.
13. Tan, Celine. 2008. *No Additionally, No Conditionality: A Critique of the World Bank's Climate Investment Funds*.
14. Third World Network (TWN). 2011. *TWN Durban News Update: Durban to decide fate of Green Climate Fund*. Thornton, Nigel. 2010. *Realizing Development*

Effectiveness: Making the Most of Climate Change Finance in Asia and the Pacific.
Capacity Development for Development Effectiveness Facility.

15. UNFCCC, Draft decision -/COP 16. 2010. Outcome of the work of the Ad Hoc Working Group on Long-term Cooperative Action under the Convention. United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). 2007a. *Climate Change: Impacts, Vulnerability and Adaptation in Developing Countries.*

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